

LIKE-A-PRO's Food Environment Citizen Innovation Living Labs

Governance Framework

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Title

LIKE-A-PRO's Food Environment Citizen Innovation Living Labs.
Governance Framework

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Project Title

LIKE-A-PRO. From niche to mainstream – alternative proteins for
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Table of Contents

1. Introduction _____	1	4. Running of the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs _____	20
1.1 LIKE-A-PRO – alternative proteins, consumer and food actor engagement	3	4.1 Type of living labs	22
1.2 What is this governance framework about?	4	4.2 The results that we aim for	23
2. THE LIKE-A-PRO Food Environment Citizen Innovation Living Labs _____	5	4.3 Examples of facilitation techniques	24
2.1 The mandate and purpose of the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs	5	5. Monitoring and Evaluation _____	26
2.2 The guiding principles of the LIKE-A-PRO living labs	7	6. Engage with us _____	27
3. The Living Labs Engagement Process _____	9	7. References _____	28
3.1 Place of implementation and target group	9		
3.2 Topics of focus and timeline of implementation	12		
3.3 Delivery team and their roles and responsibilities	18		

1. Introduction

European consumers are showing an **increasing interest in alternative food protein products** as a substitution towards the conventional animal-based foods [1]. Consumers growing pull towards such products is an **excellent opportunity to enhance efforts toward healthier and more sustainable diets**, in line with the ambitious targets of the European Green Deal [2], as well as the Farm to Fork Strategy [3].

Despite such an increasing interest, **animal-based foods still capture the majority share in our diets**, accounting for about 67% of our protein intake. For example, 94% of Europeans still consume animal-based products on a daily basis [4]. The **reasons are manifold**. As animal and alternative protein-based diets are two interconnected food consumption behaviours, their relationship favouring the former can go back to the general desire of people to consume conventional animal-based products or to other factors that are correlated directly to the latter. Research so far supports that people at points **lack information or knowledge** about the benefits (environmental, nutritional, health) of consuming alternative protein foods as a direct substitute of animal-based ones [5]; have **negative perception of the sensory properties** of alternative protein foods, together with limited **familiarity** with such products [6]; perceive alternative protein products as **not so easily accessible** (lack of choice, availability as well as convenience) [7] and as relatively **more expensive** than their counterparts [8]. When it comes to availability and choice, **the**

risk of potential allergens in such products and / or the **need for a balanced nutritional profile** becomes a consumption barrier for some consumers [6]. The **lack of a clean label, as well as guidance** on safety requirements for novel, alternative protein-based foods can also act as a barrier, especially for those consumers for whom health and safety are the determining factors of their food consumption habits [9].

Looking at food environments more closely, people perceive the **promotion and marketing efforts as limiting and / or isolating** which can then act as a barrier towards their increased consumption. For example, in most cases alternative protein products are promoted using **segregated language** such as ‘vegan’ or ‘vegetarian’, as opposed to other (animal) product / dishes where the nutritional or other sensory properties are highlighted [10]. This is especially true for consumers who might be curious but still consider themselves as carnivores. Another example is the **placement of alternative protein products** in isolated supermarket shelves or separate menu pages, a tactic that deprives these products from even the chance of being considered as possible options by consumers. Such isolation or segregation practices are followed at other points of sale (e.g., restaurants, food markets, canteens) as well [9]. Additionally, **prevalent social and cultural norms** make animal-based products to take precedence, while the consumption of alternative proteins being potentially discouraged or downplayed [10]. To cap off the exemplification of factors that disfavour the consumption of alternative protein foods are **vendor** related ones where the **availability and accessibility** to alternative food protein sources and products **becomes more difficult due to supply volatility such as shortages, gluts or failures** [11].

The above well-known barriers can at the same time act as leverage points towards the facilitation and scaling up of the consumption of alternative proteins. As an evolving field, **more research is needed** to understand consumer perceptions and how consumption of alternative protein products can be promoted. **Further research and development** should also go in the direction of alternative protein sources and the introduction of novel products and as a means to offset some of the above-identified barriers at the value / supply chain level.

1.1 LIKE-A-PRO – alternative proteins, consumer and food actor engagement

Inspired by and capitalising on these developments, the LIKE-A-PRO project aims to **accelerate the shift** towards and **normalise healthier and more sustainable dietary patterns** by **diversifying and increasing the availability, accessibility and uptake** of alternative sources of protein and specific products.

Sixteen new alternative protein products will be developed during the course of the project, based on ingredients from **seven protein sources** which are novel, sustainable, EU-based, healthy, affordable and industry viable. In addition to these products, LIKE-A-PRO will **co-design and promote other types of solutions**, such as governance mechanisms which hold the potential to promote alternative protein supply and products in food environments, including their promotion and uptake at the consumer level. Examples of these include policies that look at reducing the portfolio of unsustainable products, marketing strategies, guidelines for human-centric campaigns and similar.

Rapeseed

Mealworm

Krill

Microbial

Mushrooms

Fungus

Peas

Accordingly, **four inter-linked and iterative clusters of activities** will support reaching out the project goals:

Food environment and consumer

In this cluster, the focus is placed on better understanding consumer behaviour-related determinants, consumers' food choices and the necessary food environment (contextual) frameworks that enable a higher uptake of alternative protein products.

Alternative protein product diversification and development

In this cluster, the goal is to diversify the alternative protein supply and develop new alternative protein products, thereby increasing the availability and accessibility of such products in the European markets. Best product value propositions will be developed based on consumer, market and regulatory considerations.

Mobilising food system actors

In this cluster, the project will work with key food system actors to support them in utilising the project learnings and empower them to make alternative protein products an easy and economically viable choice via their diversified & increased market supply and favourable food environment conditions.

Impact and regulatory assessment

In this cluster, the aim is to ensure that the project will bring about positive changes in terms of health and sustainability of the European food system. Socio-economic, health, and environmental impact assessments as well as alignment with regulatory and ethical considerations are central to this clusters.

The food environment and consumer (cluster 1) and, to a lesser degree, the development of alternative protein products (cluster 2), are the clusters that will interact with the consumer engagement activities through living labs, subject of this governance framework.

1.2 What is this governance framework about?

This governance framework outlines the key procedural considerations that are necessary to factor in for the successful planning, establishment, running and monitoring of the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs. More specifically, the governance framework defines and brings together aspects related to the labs' **vision, purpose**, as well as specific **themes of focus**; the **target group**; **place** and **timeline** of implementation; **operational procedures**; and the overview of the **team** and **people delivering the labs** and their **roles and responsibilities**. It will contribute towards ensuring a

planned and systemic implementation of the living labs across the project countries, which is needed to ensure the coherence of the process and the results generated. The different sections of this report provide a more detailed elaboration of each of these aspects.

The **primary audience** of this LIKE-A-PRO living labs' governance framework are the **project's local lab implementers** in 11 European countries. Nonetheless, its **open and flexible language** allows for this governance framework to be **read by everyone who might be interested in establishing and running living labs**, beyond the context of the LIKE-A-PRO project. Complementing the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs Governance Framework and jointly laying down the foundations of the labs are the:

The LIKE-A-PRO living labs Manual

A step-by-step guideline on organising and conducting lab meetings, including the specific focus of each meeting and suggestions for facilitation techniques and other supporting materials. The Manual will act as a protocol for the various meeting and will be developed in parts preceding each lab iteration and meetings within (as seen below).

The Participant Recruitment and Engagement Strategy

Covers aspects that will help maximising citizens' participation in the living labs and supporting the lab implementers in their recruitment and then maintenance of participants' interest.

3 Train of the Trainers workshops

These are implemented for the purpose of ensuring that all local lab implementers are on the same level of understanding regarding the labs, but also have the necessary skills to deliver those.

2. THE LIKE-A-PRO Food Environment Citizen Innovation Living Labs

2.1 The mandate and purpose of the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs

The LIKE-A-PRO living labs will act as a **forum to exchange, discuss and co-create** with European citizens / consumers on a range of topics related to their food choices and the way these are made in different food environments. The specific focus and context, following the project mandate, will be the consumption and integration of alternative protein products into European diets. More specifically, through the LIKE-A-PRO living labs, the project team will ...

Explore food environments

from the **perspective of European citizens and their consumption realities** (how consumers make their choices in such environments, how easy it is, what are the challenges / opportunities and similar).

Test and receive

some **feedback on the newly developed alternative protein products** also, naturally, only where possible and while complying with all regulatory and ethical requirements in a high standard manner.

Uncover and study

the most **influential consumer behavioural determinants**, the leveraging of which has the potential to drive the shift towards healthier and more sustainable dietary patterns.

Explore and promote

entry points in food environments in the form of governance mechanisms or solutions, the introduction of which can create favourable conditions in such environments to facilitate the much-needed dietary shift.

Following such a mandate, the more specific themes of focus as well as the desired results are detailed in **Section 3.2.** and **4.2.**

2.2 The guiding principles of the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs

Connecting Research to Real Life

Living Labs aim to connect research to real-world settings, departing from the often ideal but artificial conditions of lab experiments. These real-life contexts are crucial for the development of services, products, and innovations, as they provide insights for addressing particular challenges right from the start. Additionally, in the LIKE-A-PRO living labs, consumers are engaged in various real food environments, such as supermarkets, restaurants, university canteens, and food markets, facilitating interaction and research.

Diverse Techniques for Innovation

While adapting to real-world contexts, living labs employ a multi-method approach as the various topics that are in focus direct information sharing and collaboration with lab participants. Accordingly, in LIKE-A-PRO living labs various interactive facilitation methods will be used in an iterative process to analyze consumer habits, generate ideas, co-create solutions, and understand their needs and motivations regarding alternative proteins. The specific methods will be selected during the planning and meetings of each lab iteration.

Empowerment and Collaboration

A third principle deduced from the argumentation above is that participants should not merely be passive subjects of study but be actively engaged as collaborative contributors to comprehend real-world contexts and create innovations for them. Thus, participants are regarded as experts in their field who can give recommendations and guidance, fostering a sense of ownership and self-efficacy at the same time. The latter sets the living labs approach apart from other citizen engagement formats. This third principle is taken into account especially when formulating strategies to encourage the uptake of alternative proteins into consumers' dietary choices.

Inclusivity

To create value that addresses the diverse needs and desires of all stakeholders within the given context is the primary goal of living labs. To achieve this, LIKE-A-PRO living labs tap into the diverse expertise of domain experts, even though their primary target group remains citizens. Hence, stakeholders of real food environments are taken into account to observe real-life behaviors. Importantly, the insights of these stakeholders – as well as of others like policymakers, civil society organizations, and research – will be considered in refining solutions co-created with citizens. This ensures that multiple perspectives are integrated into transparent, credible, and implementable solutions.

Added value and sustainability

The fifth principle extends from involving diverse stakeholders and creating value that serves both citizens and key stakeholders in the present and the future, aiming to outline paths for a better quality of life within environmental constraints. This understanding of sustainability is achieved by fostering continuous learning and converting the knowledge from the living labs into models, methods, and practical implications. This approach encompasses economic, ecological, and social aspects.

The principles have been developed on basis of various similar living labs handbooks and methodology outlines [\[13-17\]](#).

3. The Living Labs Engagement Process

3.1 Place of implementation and target group

The living labs will be implemented in **11 European countries** (as seen in **Figure 1**) covering different **European regions as well as dietary cultures, norms, and practices**. Throughout, we will aim to engage with European consumers from **various socio-demographic backgrounds** (more details provided in the PRES) and **geographical locations** (i.e., urban, peri-urban, and rural).

Fifteen percent of the specific participant engagement KPIs ideally will come from rural areas. In total, the project aims to minimally engage with **approx. 3.000 people**, while participants will be encouraged to participate throughout the entire living labs journey. During the engagement with the living labs' participants, the project team will uphold high ethical standards as defined in the LIKE-A-PRO's Data Management Plan as well as Ethical Requirements which are formulated on basis of and reflect the EU's GDPR regulation and other data management policies.

Figure 1. LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs locations and participation KPIs.

The exact location of the living labs is quite important for the success of such processes. **Within this project, the location will vary, depending on the need and types of the living labs** (as seen below). Hence, there are some **key guiding points and characteristics of a good location** that we will seek to cover in the project's living labs' approach to ensure that we are able to work with a diverse and inclusive participant sample. These are briefly listed below:

- Ideally central and accessible by all population groups (also applicable to food environment locations);
- Within lively neighbourhoods, ideally with the presence of community initiatives (also applicable to food environment locations);
- Non-traditional workspace studios (better for new experiences and creativity);
- Large enough to host approximately 30-40 participants with the possibility of working in smaller groups;
- Equipped with the proper facilities;
- Feasible with the planned project resources.

With regards to **food environments**, the LIKE-A-PRO living labs will seek to be present and work with the most **frequent points of sale where consumers make their food choices**. For example, supermarkets, restaurants, canteens (universities, public institutions), food and farmers markets, and similar.

3.2 Topics of focus and timeline of implementation

The implementation of the LIKE-A-PRO living labs will include 4 lab iterations with at least 2 meetings within, bringing a total of at least 8 meetings / interaction points with our participants. The Consumer Choice Framework (CCF)¹ will be the basis of our exchanges with the lab participants. The CCF brings together four overarching clusters of intervention types that can enhance our further understanding of the way food environments and consumer food choices are shaping.

¹ The Consumer Choice Framework has been developed as part of the EU funded project VALUMICS, on basis of behavioural insights / science which provide a more realistic overview of people's behaviours. Full reference: Xhelili, A. & Nicolau, M. (2021). From intention to action: multi-stakeholder recommendations for making sustainable food consumption a reality. Wuppertal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5337036

These are:

Choice editing

Interventions that influence choice by reviewing and editing out choice options that are considered unsustainable and unhealthy;

Choice environment

Interventions that influence choice by creating a favourable environment for sustainable food purchase to take place, by often nudging consumers towards a desired direction;

Choice expansion

Interventions that can guide consumers towards the sustainable and healthier options by increasing the number of the options / products available, while keeping other options open also;

Beyond choice

Interventions that are more systemic in nature and go beyond the specific point and time of food purchase, but still impact consumer choice e.g., education campaigning.

Choice
Editing

Choice
Expansion

Choice
Environment

Beyond
Choice

For more information on how the Consumer Choice Framework will be guiding the thematical exchanges with the LIKE-A-PRO living labs participants, please see **Table 1a, 1b, 1c and 1d**.

Our behaviours, including food consumption, are a result of various determinants whether they are **internal**, i.e. tied to a person’s skills, capabilities, or motivation, and / or **external**, i.e. tied to the contextual environment in which a person operates. With this in mind to generate the most optimal insights and in addition to the CCF, the living labs’ learnings and analysis will be guided on the basis of the COM-B model [18].

According to the model, **behaviours are shaped by three main determinants: capability, motivation and opportunity**. If one of these determinants is missing, a person might not undertake a specific behaviour. The three behavioural determinants are detailed below:

Figure 2: COM-B model [18]

Capability

Relates to a person’s **psychological** skills (including having the knowledge, information, memory, attention and cognitive abilities to perform a behaviour) and **physical** (bodily) skills necessary for performing the desired behaviour;

Motivation

Represents the conscious and unconscious processes that guide the way how we make decisions and then perform a behaviour. According to the model, motivation can be: **reflective** (e.g., involving a thought through planning, evaluating potential outcomes and intentions); and **automatic** (e.g., processes involving emotional reactions, desires, impulses, habits);

Opportunity

Relates to external factors, external to us as people, that might allow and make a behaviour easy or it might act as a challenge and make the performance of a behaviour more difficult. These can be either **physical** as in the infrastructural / environmental conditions (what the environment allows or facilitates in terms e.g., of time, resources, locations, availability / accessibility to a product, legislations etc.) or **social** as in the cultural norms and interpersonal relations that influence the way we understand the world.

Table 1a, 1b, 1c and 1d provides a detailed overview of some of the potential topics that we could discuss with the lab participants. Based on previous experiences, this is just a tentative focus that will be further streamlined depending on how the meetings will unfold from one iteration to the other. In addition, the topics of focus will also be

streamlined based on the results from other preceding LIKE-A-PRO project activities focused on bringing together current evidence on consumers' behavioural patterns towards alternative proteins and the typology of food environments and their readiness to promote as well as make such products available and accessible.

Table 1a. Living Labs' topical focus.

Lab iteration topical cluster	Exploratory levers
<p>Choice editing (conventional exchanges and interaction at the point of sale)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • removing meat options and making the alternative protein source the only option; • favouring of alternative protein products through public procurement; • other favouring / disfavouring financial means such as increasing the value added tax for meat, subsidising alternative protein products and / or generally make alternative protein products more price competitive.
<p>Guiding questions for choice editing (first glance, to be further refined):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do consumers react to certain limitation in product assortment? • Is the removal of certain products helpful in making consumers consume more sustainably and healthy? • Do consumers justify such an approach as a means to ensuring that sustainability and health agenda is advanced on the EU level? <p>Proposed solution to co-create with citizens:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modalities for policy actions limiting unsustainable and unhealthy food products and modalities for sustainable procurement processes. 	
<p>Timeline April – June 2024 (implementation of the labs and analysis and summary of results).</p>	

Table 1b. Living Labs' topical focus.

Lab iteration topical cluster	Exploratory levers
<p>Choice expansion (conventional exchanges and product feedback)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increasing the product assortment of (a) particular product category – co-create with consumers best product value proposition (new alternative protein products).
<p>Guiding questions for choice expansion (first glance, to be further refined):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do citizens react to such new alternative products? • Are they willing to purchase them and include them to their diets? • How informed are consumers about their edibility, health and environmental benefits? • What further additions these products need to increase consumers' willingness to buy them? • What marketing strategies and social narratives are necessary to bring these products closer to the consumer and accelerate their uptake? <p>Proposed solution to co-create with citizens:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Best product value proposition for new alternative protein products; • Guidelines for marketing alternative protein products in food environments (with choice environment below also). 	
<p>Timeline September – November 2024 (implementation of the labs and analysis and summary of results).</p>	

Table 1c. Living Labs' topical focus.

Lab iteration topical cluster	Exploratory levers
<p>Choice environment (conventional exchanges and interaction at the point of sale)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • product placement (e.g., integrated shelving) and environmental design (e.g., store, menu, e-commerce) – comparison of conventional and new alternative sources of protein; • product labelling and nutritional profiles – exploring the impact of various labelling formats on consumer behaviour, including simplified information; • making alternative proteins the default option.
<p>Guiding questions for choice environment (first glance, to be further refined):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does product placement and environmental design influence consumer behaviours/ purchasing patterns and the uptake of alternative protein products? • Does the prominence of more healthy and sustainable food options, incl. alternative protein products influence their increased consumption? • How can additional visual and audio cues as well as other behavioural insights tools (e.g., hints and tips on how to use a product in a recipe, descriptive and injunctive messaging etc.) can support the uptake of alternative protein products? • Are easier and more simple labels better at supporting consumers in changing their consumption patterns? How these should look like? How much and what type of information one needs to include? • Can a front pack label really support consumer in making more healthy and sustainable food choices? <p>Proposed solution to co-create with citizens:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Best label format proposition from a consumer perspective. 	
<p>Timeline January– March 2025 (implementation of the labs and analysis and summary of results)</p>	

Table 1d. Living Labs' topical focus.

Lab iteration topical cluster	Exploratory levers
<p>Beyond choice (conventional exchanges and interaction at the point of sale)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • communication frames, language and designing of human-centric messaging; • social norms and the role of advocates / social models; • education throughout different life stages.
<p>Guiding questions for choice environment (first glance, to be further refined):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What kind of communication campaigns are more effective in reaching out to people and /or are more impactful reinventing social narratives? • Do campaigns need to be a one-time thing or do they need to continue through time for a better outcome until the mindset has been set? • Are campaigns based on behaviours insights much more effective than their counterparts? • What is the impact of educational effort on the young people's consumption patterns and their families / households'? • How could education systems be changed to integrate sustainability considerations more prominently? <p>Proposed solution to co-create with citizens:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guidelines for communication campaigns, highlighting the most effective communication frames, language and consumer driven messages; • A framework for integrating sustainability and health principles, and alternative proteins as an enabler, in the school scheme / curricula 	
<p>Timeline April – June 2025 (implementation of the labs and analysis and summary of results)</p>	

3.3 Delivery team and their roles and responsibilities

The LIKE-A-PRO living labs and respective journey is a **comprehensive process** that involves and relies on the **active contribution of multiple partners** across the project’s countries in various roles for the labs’ effective delivery. In this process the overarching main roles one can identify are those of the **living labs, PRES** and **monitoring and evaluation coordinators**, as well as the **local lab implementers**.

Table 2a, 2b and 2c provides an overview of these roles and related responsibilities.

Table 2a. LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs roles and responsibilities.

Role	Responsibilities
<p>Living labs’ coordinator - CSCP</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design a high-level plan and governance framework for the LIKE-A-PRO living labs; • Further specify the focus, aims and outcomes of the lab meetings within the specific iteration(s); • Ensure the effective planning and organisation of the lab iterations and meetings within (guide local implementers in the design of the meeting, suggest a potential agenda and work with / support the local implementers in its tailoring, adaptation and further contextualisation, suggest / provide recommendation of facilitation techniques that could support the generation of the necessary results, support partners with the implementation of the specific techniques by providing further trainings on their utilisation); • Consult and work together with the lab local implementers for the effective implementation of the lab meetings; • Develop templates to collect the outputs and results of the lab meetings; • Seek opportunities of further improvements.

Table 2b. LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs roles and responsibilities.

Role	Responsibilities
Monitoring and evaluation – ACG-RC and CSCP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor and control the process, as well as collect and collate lessons across the different project countries; • Analyse the results and produce the consumer insights dataset.
PRES – WZV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of the participant recruitment and engagement strategy; • Development of communication materials templates, as well as messages and social media post templates; • Providing ad-hoc support to local lab implementers on questions related to recruitment and maintaining of participants' interest.

Table 2c. LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs roles and responsibilities.

Role	Responsibilities
Local lab implementers – Møreforskning, FOODCLUSTER, DEMOS, WZV, SWPS, ITC, ACG-RC, CSCP, CTIC-CITA, ZEYTINCE, UNIBO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify, recruit and bring participants to the lab meetings; • Further define and narrow down the topic of each lab meeting (in case there is a wish to go beyond the baseline agenda); • Plan, organise and run the lab meetings. The living labs' manual will provide a detailed guideline on what the meetings could look like; • Collect, analyse and report back the lab results and outputs in the specified iteration transcribing template and overarching meeting summary report; • Continue the engagement with participants, including post-meetings, to maintain interest and ensure continuous participation; • Continuously promote the labs in the respective countries and disseminate its learnings/ findings, beyond the participants also.

Some key characteristics of a local lab implementer:

- Available
- With a good network
- Excellent organisation
- Open and curious to new approaches and processes as well as input
- In possession of time
- People driven

4. Running the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs

The successful implementation of the LIKE-A-PRO living labs depends on the **partnership and establishing a solid foundation** of different angles that need to be considered in their rolling out on the ground (e.g., what, why, who, by whom, where how, when and similar). Therefore, **through the project framework, a good partnership (whom) and a first geographical selection (where)** has been sought through the LIKE-A-PRO partners and then its presence across different project countries.

In addition to the continuous partnership, we have sought to **build ad-hoc partnerships with food environment representatives** to ensure the possibility of conducting living labs in real settings and observe consumer behaviour at the point of sale. This would allow for the generation of a different results, namely, theoretical (hypothetical on people could or would act) and then more practical ones (how people are actually acting).

In addition to the partnership, for the successful implementation of the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs, as hinted in the introduction of this report, the project team will bring together a **series of interconnected documents**,

that would bring together **all necessary details for their organisation, implementation, as well as reporting of lessons learned and results**. These are:

4.1 Type of Living Lab formats

Two types of formats will comprise the LIKE-A-PRO living labs as a means towards generating the desired results and fulfilling the goals we have set out for ourselves, namely:

1. Conventional exchanges and co-creation

with lab participants where, through a variety of methods and facilitation techniques (workshop style), the project will explore consumer behaviours and uncover the main determinants that shape our food consumption patterns, including the appetite to integrate alternative proteins in our diets. Some examples of techniques are provided in **Section 4.3**, however, in a more simplified manner, the participants will exchange opinions around key questions and will be encouraged to share their insights.

2. Interaction at the point of sale

where the project team will be present at different food environments such as, indicatively, supermarkets, restaurants, canteens, food markets, to explore through e.g., interviews and surveys food consumption behaviours in their more natural habitat. The topics / research questions from **Table 1a, 1b, 1c** and **1d** will guide the exchanges here too. In such cases, the partners will engage and seek the approval of the relevant institutions so the activities can be conducted in their premises and / or in proximity.

Since in the project we are developing new products, we will aim to receive consumer feedback on those too. The feedback could be on taste and / or the rest of organoleptic qualities, as well as on packaging, where feasible. In the product tasting scenario, consumers will be presented only with those products that are produced with EFSA approved ingredients. In any other case, the feedback will be by means of the other organoleptic qualities.

For a more detailed overview of the different types or examples of questions the project intends to address with lab participants in the different living lab types or formats, please see **Table 1a, 1b, 1c** and **1d**.

4.2 The results that we aim for

The overarching aims of the LIKE-A-PRO living labs are highlighted in **Section 2.1**. Capitalising and following on such aims, through the LIKE-A-PRO living labs, the project team will be producing two overarching types of results or outputs, namely:

1. Consumer insights

which will bring together an overview of the various behavioural determinants that can influence food consumption behaviours and the possibility to integrate alternative protein foods in Europeans' diets as a means towards reaching healthier and more sustainable dietary models. The COM-B model, as well as CCF angles will be utilised to cluster and structure consumer behavioural insights. For a more interesting overview, a cross country comparative analysis will complement the country-level consumer insights dataset.

2. A variety of food environment and broader governance mechanisms

the deployment of which would enable the promotion, acceleration and mainstreaming of alternative protein products in the market. The CCF angles will guide and be the basis for the clustering and structuring of such solutions. These are presented in **Table 1a, 1b, 1c** and **1d** under the proposed solutions to be co-created with lab participants, but in a nutshell will include:

- a. Modalities for policy actions limiting unsustainable and unhealthy food products and modalities of sustainable procurement processes.
- b. Guidelines for marketing alternative protein products in food environments (with choice environment below also).
- c. Best label format proposition from a consumer perspective.
- d. Guidelines for communication campaigns, highlighting the most effective communication frames, language and consumer driven messages.
- e. A framework for integrating sustainability and health principles, and alternative proteins as an enabler, in the school scheme / curricula.

4.3 Examples of facilitation techniques

Table 3a. Examples of facilitation techniques which can be utilised throughout the different lab iterations.

Lab type	Facilitation technique	Topical Cluster	Short description
Conventional exchanges and co-creation with lab participants	Mental mapping	Choice environment, Beyond choice	Enables participants to sketch their perception of a specific area and thereby captures aspects influenced by individual experiences, motivations, and abilities. It helps to understand how local stakeholders perceive the same product [19-20].
	Fishbone diagram	Choice environment, Beyond choice	Categorizes ideas and is useful for organizing brainstorming sessions by helping to identify numerous potential causes for an issue [21, 20].
	Co-creation assemblies	All	Participants propose, discuss, and prototype desirable future scenarios. Issues are grouped into themes, each assigned to a table. At each table participants discuss the themes to reach common ground and solutions. It is important to involve a wide range of stakeholders hence aiding to understand varying perspectives [22, 20].
	Future newspapers	Choice editing, Choice expansion, Choice environment	Stimulates creativity and critical thinking by having participants envision positive future scenarios. They can then identify the elements needed to reach these scenarios, which can serve as discussion points for the group to vote on to generate alternative protein products [22, 20].
	SWOT Analysis	Choice environment, Beyond choice	As a bottom-up approach it aids product development with diverse stakeholder groups, especially in regional or municipal settings. It collects and visualizes data to portray a group's current situation [23, 19, 24].
	5 Whys	Choice environment, Beyond choice	Is an iterative questioning technique to understand cause-and-effect relationships of a problem. Its aims to identify the root of a problem by asking „Why?“ five times, with the answer to the fifth „Why?“ revealing the underlying mechanism [25, 20].
	Bright Stars	Choice editing, Choice expansion	Is a matrix framework to evaluate ideas based on their impact and likelihood of success. It is useful for prioritizing and making joint decisions when participants have numerous ideas [26, 20].

Table 3b. Examples of facilitation techniques which can be utilised throughout the different lab iterations.

Lab type	Facilitation technique	Topical Cluster	Short description
Conventional exchanges and co-creation with lab participants	Blink testing	Choice editing	A product is presented for 5 seconds and participants are asked afterwards what they associate with concrete memorized product elements. It allows to determine what visual elements are most eye-catching and how they are evaluated [27, 28].
	Brainwriting	Choice expansion, Choice environment	Participants write down their ideas about a particular question regarding the product and then pass their papers to others who read the ideas and add new ones. This cycle repeats a few times, and after that they are displayed for discussion [29, 30].
	Walt Disney Method	All	Employed to analyse problems, generate and assess ideas, and develop and review a product collaboratively. The group first slips into the role of the Dreamer who gives feedback and develops ideas of adaption without worrying about possible limitations. Then the group takes on the role of the Realist who evaluates the feasibility and practicability of the ideas while taking into account available resources, limitations, and potential challenges. Finally, they imagine themselves as the Critic and constructively engage with the realist's and dreamer's findings and identify improvement potential, points overlooked, thoughts about the product and feedback as well as advantages and risks [31, 20].
Interaction at the point of sale	Cognitive Interviews	Choice expansion, Choice environment	Consider that people tend to forget information when certain cues are absent. To counter this, they consist of four stages specifically designed to stimulate various cues, ensuring multiple retrieval pathways are activated [32].
	A / B Testing	Choice expansion, Choice environment	Enables the comparison of two versions of a product to determine which is more effective. Mainly it is about gauging user preferences between the versions. Only one component should be varying to test the effect [33, 20].
	I Like, I Wish, What If	Choice expansion, Choice environment, Beyond choice	Collects open feedback by letting participants complete the following statements: „I Like...“ statements encourage participants to provide positive feedback on the product, while „I Wish...“ statements collect suggestions for improvements and constructive criticism. „What If...“ statements allow participants to share innovative ideas which might not be directly related to the product [34, 20].
	Shopping with customers	Choice expansion, Choice environment, Beyond choice	By conducting in-depth interviews before and after accompanying participants repeatedly in a retail setting [35, 36].

An illustration of two people sitting at a dark blue table in a room filled with various indoor plants. The person on the left is wearing a dark blue long-sleeved shirt and dark pants, sitting on a blue stool. The person on the right is wearing an orange long-sleeved shirt and dark pants, also sitting on a blue stool. They are both looking at laptops on the table. The room has a light-colored wall with several framed pictures of plants and a hanging plant. The floor is a mix of yellow and white. The overall style is modern and clean.

5. Monitoring and Evaluation

Throughout the entire process of implementing the LIKE-A-PRO living labs, monitoring and evaluation will be undertaken to ensure the living labs are planned, implemented and reported upon as envisioned. More specifically, through this process, the project team will ensure the:

- scope and timeline of the planned activities are being followed and respected;
- appropriate number of participants are engaged from one lab iteration to the other;
- appropriate results are being generated;
- procedural implementation is effective, and challenges and opportunities are identified as well as corrective actions are undertaken to mitigate the challenges but then exploit the opportunities also;
- collection and analysis of the learnings takes place, both procedural and content, across the 11 project countries and identify synergies and trade-offs between them;
- impact of the living labs on the participants is understood.

Different monitoring and evaluation mechanisms will be deployed to reach the various aims of the monitoring and evaluation process. The monitoring and evaluation efforts and related mechanisms will be coordinated by the living labs and monitoring and evaluation coordinators, with the support and active contribution of the local implementers (as seen in **Table 2a, 2b** and **2c**).

An illustration of a modern cafe or grocery store. In the foreground, a woman with long dark hair, wearing a red top and black pants, sits on a black stool at a small black table. She is holding a white coffee cup. Opposite her, a man with a beard, wearing a yellow shirt and black pants, sits on a black stool, also holding a white coffee cup. They appear to be in conversation. In the background, there are shelves stocked with various products, including bottles and boxes. A man in a yellow shirt is standing behind a counter, looking at a laptop. The scene is lit with warm, yellow light, and there are large green leaves in the upper corners.

6. Engage with us

As drivers of demand, consumers hold a central role in the market and our operational frameworks. Therefore, when it comes to sustainability, in general, and the promotion of alternative proteins as a means to reaching food sustainability, it is pivotal to engage with them, hear and understand their needs and wishes, as well as bring them around the table as important stakeholders for more credible, transparent, effective and long-lasting solutions.

The LIKE-A-PRO project comes close to such active consumer participation and engagement by means of living labs that will be established in 11 European countries (Norway, Denmark, Finland, The Netherlands, Poland, Slovenia, Greece, Germany, Spain, Turkey and Italy) covering all European regions: South, North, West and East.

Simultaneous to consumer engagement, it is equally important for food system actors and practitioners to also collaborate and forge partnerships for a holistic consideration of different parts of the food system. Collaborations among food actors / decision makers is also helpful for a maximal outreach to consumers.

Accordingly, if you are located in one of the LIKE-A-PRO living labs countries and / or generally have an interest to collaborate with us on this project activity, please feel free to reach out.

(Un)Sustainability, including the food one, affects all of us, hence, it is only fair and recommendable that we all chip in with our efforts and innovative ideas to making better food consumption patterns and overall, a good life a reality!

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LIKE-A-PRO's Food Environment Citizen Innovation Living Labs

Governance Framework

Building a better world
through alternative
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